

Annex to Memorandum of Understanding between ELIXIR and Euro-BioImaging

TECHNICAL AND STRATEGIC ACTION PLAN

I. Introduction

This Technical Annex outlines the areas of collaboration between the ELIXIR and Euro-BioImaging research infrastructures, focusing on their respective strengths and shared interests. By working together, we aim to leverage our expertise and capabilities to advance imaging technologies, promote data sharing and interoperability, and foster a culture of open science.

II. Areas of Collaboration

Databases	Increased interoperability of Euro-BioImaging image data resources like BioImage Archive, IDR and EMPIAR with ELIXIR biomolecular databases. Key importance of connecting to ELIXIR Deposition Databases, like BioStudies and BioSamples for correlative/multimodal data. ELIXIR experience in data management and integration combined with Euro-BioImaging expertise in managing large datasets and delivering services to specific users.
Standards, Ontologies and Interoperability	Develop aligned platforms, ontologies, technical interfaces, and schemas for connecting and integrating data resources from both infrastructures. For example further development and support of ontologies like EDAM Bioimaging and encourage use of RO-Crate and BioSchemas to structure metadata and promote interoperability.
Workflows and HPC	Euro-BioImaging can leverage ELIXIR expertise in software stewardship and the development of Research Software Quality Toolkit (RSQkit) to support professionalisation of Galaxy, Python, Java, and NextFlow workflows for image data analysis. In particular, the WorkFlowHub repository supports sharing of workflows and Euro-BioImaging provides

	community and cross-domain support via its Image data workflows Expert Group.
Emerging technologies	Foster multimodal data, spatial omics data, structural biology data (together with Instruct-ERIC) and synthetic data for imaging technologies.
AI	Promote AI developments through AI4Life, ELIXIR Machine Learning focus group, Research Data Alliance FAIR4ML Interest Group, BioImage Model Zoo, DOME Registry, etc.
Medical Data	Initiatives for cancer-related data sharing (e.g. EUCAIM, GDI). ELIXIR experience in data management and sharing and Euro-BioImaging experience in image data and metadata generation, quality control, annotation etc.
Cross-RI projects	Shared participation in EC projects, actual and proposed, between Euro-BioImaging and ELIXIR Hub and Nodes.
Data Spaces	Aligned contributions to European Open Science Cloud, European Health Data Spaces etc.
Impact	Shared impact assessment practices on the benefits of data management and integration across both infrastructures.
Training and Capacity Building	Align training programs that cover both technical and soft skills, including mentorship, job shadowing, and the professionalisation of RI careers.

III Implementation

The implementation plan will be developed in collaboration with both ELIXIR and Euro-BioImaging teams, focusing on the following [types of] activities:

1. Identify key individuals to oversee the collaboration.
2. Conduct joint workshops and meetings between Euro-BioImaging Expert Groups and ELIXIR Platforms and Communities to discuss progress and identify areas for improvement.
3. Develop common platforms and ontologies for integrating data resources.
4. Collaborate on training programs and capacity-building initiatives.
5. Shared events
 - Regular site visits between ELIXIR and Euro-BioImaging

- Attendance and representation at respective All Hands Meetings
 - Shared Hackathons, such as EDAM BioImaging
6. Shared outputs & publications
- Project Outputs
 - Position Papers
 - Reports